

ADVANCEMENTS IN NANOTHERANOSTICS FOR CANCER: INNOVATIONS IN DIAGNOSIS AND THERAPY

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Abstract:

Cancer is becoming the most feared and dreaded disease. WHO states that this is the second leading cause of death. Despite the development of various treatment and diagnostic methods, cancer still poses a serious threat to human health. Therefore, research continues and leads to the development of new techniques such as nanotheranostics (combination of treatment and diagnosis). Cancer nanotheranostics is a promising field that combines nanotechnology with medical and diagnostic capabilities, revolutionizing cancer diagnosis and treatment. This review explores the functional models of nanoparticles that can be used as both therapeutic and diagnostic agents. They include gold and silver-based, graphene-based, lipid and polymer-based and protein-based nanoparticles, etc., while reducing side effects, showing good potential for cancer diagnosis and treatment. These nanoparticles can deliver drugs to the tumor and can also be used for radiation therapy, photothermal therapy, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computed tomography (CT), and fluorescence imaging to improve early diagnosis. This review describes their use in the diagnosis of various cancers, including breast, lung, thyroid, stomach, and hematological malignancies. It emphasizes their effectiveness in enhancing the accuracy of imaging techniques and making medicine a reality. It provides insight into the future directions of nanotheranostic platforms, demonstrates the potential for personalized cancer treatment, and the creation of multifunctional nanoparticles to improve clinical outcomes in clinical cancer management.

Keywords:

Cancer, nanotheranostics, nanoparticles, photothermal therapy (PTT), MRI, computed tomography(CT), Fluorescence imaging, Cancer imaging, Tumor drug delivery

Introduction:

"Theranostics" is a word derived from the combination of "therapy" and "diagnosis". As the name suggests, the system offers simultaneous delivery of therapeutic loads and diagnostic (imaging) agents, which enables real-time monitoring of drug biodistribution, pharmacokinetics, and also aids in monitoring subsequent pathological manifestations in response to a therapeutic drug. The extremely small size and improved physicochemical properties of nanosystems offer scope for the convergence of therapeutic and diagnostic systems on a common platform. Cancer accounts for a major proportion of disease-related mortality worldwide. Cancer in pathological terms can be defined as an unregulated rapid proliferation of abnormal cells that could potentially invade a new location at later stages. Based on these potentials, cancer was further categorized as benign (non-invasive) and malignant (invasive). Of these two classes, it is the malignancy with metastatic potential that accounts almost exclusively for cancer-related morbidity. Due to the ever-increasing incidence and mortality, it has become one of the biggest challenges for longer life expectancy worldwide. Although in developed countries such as the United States, overall cancer incidence and mortality have gradually declined over the past decade due to new research into tumor mechanisms, improved diagnostic tools, and new therapeutic strategies, the burden of cancer remains a major challenge in development as well as developed economies. We urgently need more breakthrough innovations and ever-improving tactics, along with a better understanding and use of existing cancer treatment strategies. Most patients with malignant tumors have received conventional treatment, including surgery, radiotherapy and chemotherapy, either in combination or alone. Although surgery is considered an irreplaceable treatment for most solid localized tumors, when metastases occur, systematic treatment is required as a supplement. Radiation therapy is used in more than half of cancer patients and is one of the most effective treatment modalities, but remains a huge challenge to mitigate short- and long-term toxicity. Traditional chemotherapy also faces major challenges due to its inherent properties such as instability, insolubility, drug resistance, and significant tissue damage. Traditional systemic drug delivery also puts all somatic cells at risk of toxicity. However, there are ways to reduce the side effects and avoid the disadvantages of chemotherapy by confining drugs to a small space, absorbing the drug into well-designed pores or media, providing a relatively stabilized microenvironment, allowing active interactions in the body with the help of a biomimetic membrane, and releasing drugs after transport to the desired sites. This is what nanotechnology is trying to do.

Nanotheranostics is a relatively new, rapidly developing field that combines the advantages of treatment and diagnosis through a single nanocarrier. The ability to combine therapeutic and diagnostic capabilities into a single package offers exciting prospects for the development of nanomedicine. Nanotherapy can deliver treatment while monitoring treatment response in real-time, reducing the possibility of overdosing or underdosing. Once conceptually advanced, nanomedicine has been explored for use in a large number of diseases, particularly in effective anticancer drug delivery, diagnostics, and imaging. The combination of nanotechnology and conventional tumor therapy can not only improve the properties of chemoradiotherapy drugs, but also reduce the incidence of poisoning and other side effects. Several nanoparticle (NP) therapeutic platforms, such as liposomes, albumin, and polymeric micelles, have been approved by regulatory authorities for cancer treatment. These NPs can rapidly cross human biological barriers, even in a targeted manner, and continuously release contents to maintain an appropriate drug concentration in the blood. The growing interest in the production of new formulations inside NPs can avoid the disadvantages of traditional treatment and nanotechnology and promote preclinical and clinical efficacy.

Fig. 1 Nanomedicine in cancer diagnosis and treatment. CT computed tomography, MRI magnetic resonance imaging, PET positron emission tomography, SPECT single-photon emission tomography, US ultrasound, FI fluorescence imaging. [106]

Types of nanoparticles:

Types of NPs		Pro's	Con's
Polymeric NPs	Natural polymers	Biocompatibility and degradability ,Excellent transmucosal capability	Low stability
	Synthetic polymers	High stability, bioavailability and loading capacity	Tissue accumulation, Low degradability, Unfavorable side effects
Inorganic NPs	Mesoporous silica	Easy functionalization and surface modification, High capacity of storing drugs, Simple production process	High costs
	Gold NPs	Low toxicity, High stability, Simple synthesis, Bioconjugation of desired molecules, Efficient light to heat conversion	Prone to accumulating in tissue and toxicity potential, Unsatisfactory clinic treatment outcomes
	Carbon nanomaterials	Excellent optical properties, Thermal conductivity, Electrical conductivity, Chemical stability, Functionalization	Potential problems to biosafety
Liposomes		Excellent biocompatibility, Wide adaptability to drugs, Reduced adverse effects, avoiding bioclearance of agents	Low storage of lipophilic molecules, opsonization, immunogenicity and instability, Highcosts
Micelles		Alleviating toxicity ,Enabling transportation of lipophilic drugs, Reducing the uptake by macrophages, Prolonging the circulation time, Targeting drug release	Instability invivo, Low solubility of small size particles, Low drug loading capacity
Hydrogels		High biocompatibility, High drug loading capacity, Controllable and adjustable of drug release, Highly adjustable chemical and physical properties	Fast clearance, Off-target accumulation
Extracellular vesicles		Targeted drug delivery, High biocompatibility, Loading a large variety of cargos	Difficult for isolation, purification and differential recognition, Abnormal accumulations in the liver
Virus		Outstanding targeting capability, Potential in immunotherapy or vaccination strategies	Lacking of clinical translation
Natural membrane coatedNPs		Prolonging the blood circulation time, Evading clearance from immune system, Boosting therapeutic effects, Improving target capabilities	Complexity of scale-up manufacturing, Accumulating in liver or reticuloendothelial systems, Difficulties with purification and storage

Nanotechnology in cancer theranostics

This combination of therapy and diagnosis is known as "theranostics". The term was introduced in 2002 by Funkhouser [20,21] to explain the integration of concurrent diagnostic and treatment modalities in the same dose range [22,23]. Theranostic strategies have shown enormous potential in monitoring targeted drug delivery. The physical properties of the theranostic agent must allow for easy biological probing while remaining stable under physiological conditions after delivery. The agent must also be able to penetrate any biological barrier encountered on its way to the intended tissue or organ without significant toxic side effects [24]. A theranostic agent must consist of a therapeutic drug (eg: nucleic acid such as miRNA or siRNA, therapeutic proteins or any other chemotherapeutic agent), a therapeutic cargo carrier, targeting ligands and signal emitters (with unique radioactive, optical or magnetic properties), all of which may be covalently or non-covalently conjugated to the application platform. For example, radionuclide coupled with personalized therapy has emerged as an important platform in cancer treatment. Here, the therapeutic radionuclides Y-90 and Lu-177 are labeled with the tracer Ga-68 and used to diagnose neuroendocrine tumors using positron emission tomography (PET) or CT scan.

Photodynamic therapy

Photodynamic therapy (PDT) is a type of phototherapy where non-toxic, light-sensitive compounds are converted into toxic substances when exposed to selective wavelengths of light. These compounds are known as photosensitizers and their toxicity (phototoxicity) is used to treat tumors and other pathological malignancies [25]. Phthalocyanines (Pc) and porphyrins are used to direct PDT and induce a photosensitizing response to treat various age-related macular diseases, while also being used in antimicrobial and antiviral therapeutic applications [26]. Pc-based theranostic agents show limited efficacy in their use for cancer treatment and imaging due to the inability to solubilise Pc compounds. The utility of Pc in-vitro after complexation with a dendrimer-based nanoplatform to dramatically increase water solubility has been shown to have low dark toxicity (no light activation) and high light toxicity (10 min using a 700 nm laser), while when used as in-vivo imaging agent, showed high-contrast imaging in a xenograft mouse model of ovarian cancer.

Fig. 2. An outline of the basic functional scheme of a nanotheranostic agent. Theranostic nanoparticles are delivered to cancer cell, where they therapeutically exterminate the cell while emitting signals that can be detected and monitored using a suitable diagnostic system (steps 1–4). [107]

Magnetic Nanotheranostic agents

Multipurpose applications such as MRI and multimodal imaging (PET, optical imaging), efficient delivery of both gene and conventional chemotherapy, as well as hyperthermal killing of cancer cells [27,28]. MNPs offer a smaller size (100 nm) MNPs have been widely used to treat glioblastoma through targeted drug delivery, reduction of tumor growth, and monitoring of MNP accumulation in tumor tissue using contrast-enhanced MRI imaging. To increase the multifunctionality of IONPs, Sahu and colleagues [29] used Ce³⁺-sensitized gadolinium phosphate (GdPO₄) nanotubes doped with a PEGylated (conjugated with polyethylglycol; PEG) Tb³⁺ coating on IONPs together with glutamine. Due to the mesoporous nature and the presence of a large amount of negatively charged functional groups on the surface, this multifunctional nanorice has been shown to be an effective carrier of chemotherapeutic drugs such as doxorubicin (Dox) [30]. The nanorice emits green light, with which its cellular uptake and accumulation can be observed and monitored using confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM). The effect of these modified Dox-loaded IONPs was studied in vitro using MCF-7 (human breast cancer) and HeLa (human cervical cancer) cell lines. These Dox-loaded IONPs show a promising future increase in the therapeutic efficacy of these cancers.

Photothermal therapy

Photothermal therapy (PTT) is a non-invasive therapeutic approach with a number of advantages, such as increased selectivity, reduced systemic toxicity and the possibility of remote control [31]. PEGylated molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂) flakes (MS flakes) integrated with IONPs (Fe₃O₄) were used as in vivo theranostic agents. Dual modal functionality is achieved using the photothermal ability of the MS flakes to convert near-infrared (NIR) light to heat and the magnetic properties of the IONPs to guide the particle to the desired tissue using an external magnetic field. This combinatorial approach makes MRI and photoacoustic tomography (PAT) cancer imaging and diagnosis a viable treatment option. Further modification of MoS₂-iron oxide nanocomposites (MoS₂-IO) through surface absorption of the positron radioisotope ⁶⁴Cu can further be used as a PET theranostic agent. This setup provides a powerful in vivo system capable of photothermal ablation (MoS₂), magnetically guided delivery (IONP) and 3D imaging of the body/physiological processes (⁶⁴Cu) and enables imaging of tumor growth and metastasis. MoS₂-IO-(d)PEG, which are MoS₂-IONanocomposites modified by double PEGylation, showed potential in PTT (via laser irradiation) for tumor ablation in 4T1 (mouse breast carcinoma) cells.

Tumors from mice injected with MoS₂-IO-(d)PEG and exposed to the NIR laser were obliterated by an increase in surface temperature of approximately 51 C in 5 min, whereas the temperature was observed to increase only 5 C with laser exposure in absence of MoS₂-IO-(d)PEG. IONPs (and their modified versions) enhance image contrast in MRI applications [32]. For example, superparamagnetic IONPs (SPIONs) with amphiphilic poly(styrene)-b-poly(acrylic acid)-Dox and folic acid can be used as potential theranostic agents, as demonstrated in SkBr3 (human breast cancer cells) and HCT116 (human colon cancer) cell lines for controlled release, targeting and anticancer activity [34]. PEGylated SPIONs conjugated with HuCC49DCH2 antibody and 5-FAM (a fluorescent dye) demonstrated enhanced cancer cell targeting due to increased molecular size. For example, HuCC49DCH2-SPIONs can be used to encapsulate drugs and be delivered in a pH-dependent manner to the target tissue, while being monitored by MRI, fluorescence imaging and Prussian blue staining [35]. Such fluoromagnetic NPs have been used in the selective monitoring of FR+ MCF-7 cells without recognizing FR cells such as A549 lung carcinoma cells [36]. A Rubik-like magnetic nanocomposite can be used as an anticancer nanotheranostic agent containing four iron oxide nanocubes capped with oleic acid and conjugated with a PEG-modified dioleate. It was successfully tested in murine melanoma cells (B16F10) where it enhanced the antitumor efficacy of paclitaxel (PCL) as monitored by a 1.5 T MRI scanner. silica (WS₂-IO@MS-PEG) can be used for efficient drug delivery, therapy (demonstrated in 4T1 tumor-bearing female Balb/c mice), and trimodal (MRI, fluorescence, and X-ray CT) image-guided monitoring in the presence of NIR/X-ray. 4T1 breast cancer cells can also be treated with gFe₂O₃@Au magnetic gold nanoflowers (MG-Nfs).

Gold and silver Nanotheranostic agents

Nanotheranostic agents based on gold and silver Gold and silver NPs have revealed colossal promise as theranostics. They offer the advantages of facile synthesis, bioconjugation and surface modifications that confer AuNPs biocompatibility and make them less cytotoxic [37]. In 2009, Natarajan et al. reported a novel AuNP-based assembly for the treatment of breast cancer, which consisted of the conjugation of miR-491 (a novel microRNA), quantum dots (Qdots; imaging agent), and streptavidin/biotin linked to a chimeric mouse-human monoclonal IgG1 antibody (mAb) ChL6 (MAb -ChL6). The process was monitored using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) [38]. AuNPs are assembled with amine-terminated poly(-amidoamine) dendrimers conjugated to PEGylated folic acid (to improve specific targeting of FR-overexpressing cancer cells), PEG-modified α -tocopherylsuccinate (to target the mitochondrial electron transport chain and subsequent apoptosis), and FITC (for visualization of cellular uptake of the nanosystem using confocal microscopic imaging and CT scanning) [39]. Gold nanobeacons (AuNBs) have high specificity, enhanced cellular uptake and negligible cytotoxicity [40]. AuNBs, conjugated with surface-bound 30-Cy3 and 50-thiol-C6, can be used for specific mRNA silencing, while the amplification in fluorescence after surface binding is directly proportional to the level of silencing. This was demonstrated in HCT116 cells where such AuNBs were used to silence enhanced green fluorescent protein (EGFP) [41]. AuNBs can effectively silence the expression of a single gene, very similar to traditional siRNA; but alternatively they can also be used in the targeting and silencing of siRNA (exogenous) and miRNA (endogenous) [42].

Gold nanoclusters such as FluorescentAuNCs conjugated to chitosan biopolymers emit green and blue fluorescence that can be used for imaging and detected by recording the uv-vis spectrum. These NPs have the ability to deliver therapeutic agents to the target tissue. For example, AuNCs loaded with the CDUPRT (cytosine deaminase-uracilphosphoribosyltransferase) suicide gene can kill HeLa cells by adding the precursor 5-fluorocytosine (5-FC), which is converted to the pro-apoptotic toxin 5-fluorouracil. Cancer cell targeting has been investigated by fluorescence microscopy and flow cytometry. Again, AuNPs coated with ligands (peptides) for transferrin receptor (TfR) and EGFR together with Pc 4 (a photosensitizer) can be used as a potential nanotheranostic agent in glioblastoma, as demonstrated in human U87-MG glioma cells that overexpress the receptors TfR and EGFR.

Graphene-based nanotheranostic agents

The advantages of graphene nanotherapeutics are a large surface area, colloidal stability, easy surface modification/functionalization, as well as excellent electrical and mechanical properties. Image-guided tumor ablation by synergistic PTT can be achieved using graphene-based nanotherapeutic agents such as graphene nanosheets, which demonstrated increased apoptosis in CD44+ KB carcinoma cells using NIR imaging (with indocyanine green as NIR imaging agent) [43]. Gadolinium-conjugated -GO (Gd-NGO), which has a positively charged nanosurface, can be used to interact with the negatively charged miRNA Let-7 g (MIRLET7G, a putative RNAi agent) to form Gd-NGO/Let7 g complexes, which have demonstrated antineoplastic properties. Gd-NGOs have also been shown to effectively transport the anthracycline antitumor drug epirubicin (EPI). GdNGO-Let7g-EPI can simultaneously be used as an effective contrast agent for both drug site monitoring and quantitative analysis by MRI. Dendrimer-based low-oxygen graphene (Pc-LOG) nanoparticles have been shown to have multimodal function (Pc photodynamic, LOG photothermal) in the treatment of unresectable ovarian tumors.

When applied systemically, Pc-LOG NPs can image unresected tumor margins and, using NIR light irradiation, ablate cancer cells via PTT. Thus, graphene-based nanotheranostic strategies show enormous potential for clinical application, especially in cancer therapy. Liao et al.³⁴⁷ developed a nanocomposite consisting of ND conjugated with paclitaxel (PTX) and cetuximab (Cet) to specifically target EGFR-positive triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) cells. Their study showed that the ND-PTX-Cetnanocomposite effectively induced mitotic catastrophe and apoptosis in TNBC cells by targeting the EGFR receptor. This finding suggests that the ND-PTX-Cetnanocomposite could be a promising therapeutic strategy for TNBC. Additionally, the flexibility in modifying functional groups on NDs and the natural fluorescence of fluorescent nanodiamonds (FNDs) make NDs a compelling platform for the creation of biomedical imaging and clinical diagnostic tools. CNTs can undergo various surface treatments to improve their functionality. The combination of this property together with the intrinsic advantages of CNTs, such as their high flexibility, tensile strength, and electrical conductivity, make CNTs a desirable platform for various biological applications. Covalent functionalization of CNTs is used to create stimulus-responsive engineering cap. In this technique, gold NPs were designed to plug the open ends of multiwalled CNTs (MWCNTs). The caps consisted of 40 nm gold nanoparticles that were attached to oxidized CNTs via linkers that responded to biochemical stimuli. These stimuli include changes in pH (achieved through a hydrazone bond that breaks under acidic conditions in tumors), a highly reducing environment (achieved by a disulfide bond that breaks down in the presence of higher levels of intracellular glutathione), and esterase concentrations (achieved through an ester bond). High-resolution imaging verified the existence of gold NPs mostly at the ends of the CNTs, indicating the successful formation of a covalent bond between the gold nanoparticles and the open tips of the CNTs.

Silicon-based nanotheranostic agents

The characteristic properties of silica NPs (SiNPs), such as chemical and thermal stability, large surface area and pore volume, biocompatibility (due to easy surface functionalization, surface reactivity) and biodegradability, make them important as nanotherapeutic agents [44]. The porosity of siNPs provides their greatest advantage as a theranostic platform. Porosity control enables controlled, sequential and multifunctional delivery of theranostic cargo to different types of cancer cells. miRNA-21 has been implicated in a number of pathological conditions, including cardiovascular disease, lung disorders, and cancer [45]. Bu-S-AS/MB nanocomposite was observed to inhibit miRNA-21 and induce apoptosis through caspase activation. This phenomenon can be simultaneously monitored using a molecular beacon [46]. Silica nanorattles conjugated with LHRH-PE40 (luteinizing hormone-releasing hormone-Pseudomonas aeruginosa exotoxin40) and docyanine green fusion protein can be used as nanotherapy in combination with docetaxel (an antimetabolic chemotherapeutic agent). LHRH directs nanocomposites to cancer cells [47], followed by inhibition of cell proliferation by docetaxel and cytotoxic activity of PE40 [48]. The docyanine green signal is recorded for image-guided drug delivery and specific cancer therapy. Silica nanoclamps conjugated with very high doses of camptothecin (CPT), a human DNA topoisomerase I inhibitor [49], Dox and Qdots have shown considerable potential as a nanotheranostic agent for the treatment of pancreatic cancer. Cancer cell viability is significantly reduced by the combined effects of CPT and Dox. The fluorescence quenching of both CPT and Dox under normal conditions and fluorescence recovery in slightly acidic media can be used to sense drug release in cells. Cellular uptake and delivery of drugs can be analyzed by confocal laser scanning microscopy and simultaneous imaging of cancer cells [50]. Similarly, mesoporous SiNPs (MSNs) conjugated with lanthanides such as europium (Eu) and Gd have been tested as theranostics. MSN. In conjugation with CPT, EuGd-MSN (now EuGd-MSN-CPT) has been used to target cancer cells and simultaneously diagnose the impact of the application using MRI and fluorescence imaging [51]. In a recent study [52], substituted silicon naphthalocyanine (SiNc) was modified into a biocompatible nanopatform (SiNc-NP) by tailoring it with polypropylene iminedendrimer encapsulation and surface PEGylation. SiNc-NP was then used in chemotherapy treatment.

Lipid- and polymer-based nanotheranostic agents

Lipids (e.g., liposomes and solid lipid nanoparticles) [53–55] and polymers (e.g., dendrimers, polymeric nanoparticles, and polymeric micelles) [56–58] have often been used as nanocarriers, due to easy adaptation in vivo (e.g., PEGylation), cycle life, targeting ability, thermodynamic stability, generation stimuli and diagnostic applications [59–61]. PEGylated liposomes conjugated with IONPs and an infrared dye (DiR) are extremely promising asternotic agents (L-IONP/DiR) due to their dual in vivo imaging modes, superparamagnetic MRI and fluorescence imaging in the NIR loaded L-IONP/Dir with anti-human PGN635 monoclonal antibody (specific for phosphatidylserine, which is exposed in tumor endothelial blood cells blood vessels but not in normal tissue endothelial cells, leading to PGN-L-IONP/DiRnanocomposite inhibiting the growth of MDA-MB-231 (breast) tumor cells. PGN-L-IONP/DiR was diagnosed by optical imaging and MRI [63] Surfactant-stabilized oil-core nanocapsules carrying a chemotherapeutic drug (colchicine) and a fluorescent probe (coumarin-6) have also been used for bioimaging and treatment of various cancer cell types including MCF-7, A549 and MEWO (melanoma cells) and simultaneous monitoring of tumor size by Gd-conjugated NPs ions and biotinylated antibodies of the vascular endothelial growth factor receptor may be an apromising agent with a nanotherapeutic effect - the hepatocellular carcinoma drug sorafenib.

It inhibits various protein kinases such as receptor tyrosine kinases and serine or threonine kinases. The efficacy of such nanoclusters has been shown to be pH sensitive, as reported in H22 (mouse hepatoma) cells [65]. CD44 receptor positive MDA-MB-231 cells showed significant toxicity when treated with chondroitin sulfate A NPs conjugated with Dox-deoxycholic acid. Redox-triggered NPs loaded with poly(disulfide amide) and L-cysteine-based docetaxel have been reported to hold significant theranostic promise in HeLa, A549, MCF-7 and DU145 (prostate cancer) cell lines as diagnosed/monitored by TEM imaging. Other recent studies [66] suggested the use of albumin-modified Gd-nanocomposites as theranostic agents, both in vitro and in vivo. In another report [67], galactose-based nanogels were used for targeted delivery of iodoazomycin arabinofuranoside to solid hypoxic hepatocellular carcinoma. Similarly, lactosomes conjugated with an indocyanine green derivative were also used for PDT of gastric cancer lymph node metastases [68]. The most widely used biomaterial based on polysaccharides in the architecture of nanomedicine is chitosan. Chitosan is a water-soluble, biocompatible, and biodegradable polysaccharide material obtained from crustacean shells. Due to its excellent transmucosal ability, chitosan-based biomaterials are commonly used for drug delivery systems across various epithelia such as the eye and intestine. Yeh et al. found that chitosan can “permeabilize” the mucosal epithelium by mediating the opening of the tight junction between mucosal cells so that a drug or other therapeutic component can pass through the mucosal barrier and act on the malignant tissue. Therefore, the oral route of administration is widely recognized as the most convenient and convenient approach for patients. Another advantage of chitosan is that it can inspire other researchers to modify or design completely new biomaterials with chitosan. In recent research, new design of chitosan named AuNP-siRNA-glycol nanoparticles-chitosan-taurocholic acid (AR-GT NP) was used to treat liver metastases from colorectal cancer in an animal study. This delivery system has the potential for the treatment of liver-related tumors. Moreover, chitosan itself has the potential to be an adjunctive therapy for upregulating immune system function during tumor treatment procedures. According to Carroll et al., chitosan can induce type I interferons (IFNs) to promote dendritic cell maturation and increase Th1 sensitivity through the cGAS and STING pathways.

Protein-based nanotheranostic agents

HSA has several key characteristics, including: (1) it's an endogenous carrier of the body, so it does not cause any inflammatory and corresponding toxic response; (2) it is a natural carrier of various ions and compounds in the circulatory system; (3) it has a long circulation time, so it can be designed to release drugs gradually [14]; (4) can be biodegraded and reproduced by metabolism [15]; (5) tends to accumulate at the site of abnormal vasculature, including leakage or capillaries in the TME; (6) cancer cells that require multiple types of substances to grow are likely to approach HSA. [69,71] Protein-based nanotheranostics Modified protein nanocages have been used as carriers for therapeutic and diagnostic agents [74,75]. These nanoparticles can be modified on their internal and external surfaces due to their protein nature. Internal surface modifications allow loading of conjugable molecules (drugs/aptamers/contrast agents) and external surface modifications facilitate ligand conjugation. E2 nanoparticles are naturally occurring protein nanoparticles (24 nm) formed in the core of the pyruvate dehydrogenase multienzyme complex in *Bacillus stearothermophilus*, which can be used as flexible scaffolds carrying theranostics. Like E2 protein nanoparticles, ferritin nanoparticles have also found an important place in cancer therapy [74]. The ferritin heavy (H)-chain has a natural affinity for the human transferrin receptor-1 (CD71), which is overexpressed in tumor cells. This characteristic feature of ferritin can be exploited to find increased specificity of ferritin nanoparticles for cancer cells, thereby increasing the likelihood of effective targeted delivery of theranostic agents. Drug-induced self-assembly of modified albumins [72]. A protein-based PTT-theranostic agent was designed by developing a nanocomposite containing a modified heptamethine dye labeled with human serum albumin (HSA) [73]. Also, other proteins such as gelatin, collagen, elastin, gliadin, legumin and zein along with whey, milk and soy proteins have been used as nanodrug/signaling agent carriers. At the same time, a recent novel strategy for the synthesis of semiconductor nanocrystals using protein nanoreactors has also shown potential as a therapeutic agent against cancer [76].

Red blood cells-NPs

Erythrocyte-derived nanoparticles, also called RBC membrane-coated nanoparticles (RBC-NPs), are commonly investigated as drug delivery vehicles. RBC-NPs have demonstrated several advantages compared to normal drug delivery systems: (i) increased blood circulation time of loaded drugs; (ii) preventing clearance from the immune system (iii) enhancing the therapeutic effects of loaded drugs and (iv) improving the ability of targeted cancer cells to integrate biomimetic modifications. [78-84] Jiang et al. fused the membrane of erythrocytes with the membrane of MCF-7 (a breast cancer cell line) to create hybrid melanin particles for in vivo photothermal treatment. Improved antitumor properties along with several advantages such as high biocompatibility and limited immunogenicity.

NANOMEDICINE IN CANCER DIAGNOSIS

IN DIGESTIVE SYSTEM TUMORS

The nanosensor is a highly sensitive and specific method of tumor detection. Loynachan et al. designed a multi-protease nanosensor for exogenous drug release. The sensor takes renally purified catalytic AuNCs as a template and links them to a neutral avidin protein scaffold via a biotinylated protease-cleavable peptide connector to form an AuNC-NAV complex that is stable in vivo without interference and retains catalytic activity. It was dissected for impaired protease activity at the affected site, including the serine protease thrombin and zinc-dependent matrix metalloproteinase 9 (MMP9), among which the MMP-responsive nanosensor AuNC-P2 20-NAV was cleaved by MMP at the tumor site, abnormally higher MMP expression, and released AuNC of about 2 nm in size. AuNC was released into the urine by renal filtration, and then the disease state was simply and sensitively detected by detecting the ability of AuNC to catalyze the peroxidase substrate. The results showed that the colorimetric signal of the urine of mice with colon cancer was stronger than that of healthy mice, and the specificity of the biomarkers was overcome by monitoring the protease activity. At the same time, the nanosensor can be eliminated by renal excretion without being toxic. Tang et al. designed a SERS-responsive silver nanoparticle film for the simultaneous detection of α -fetoprotein and glypican-3, which improved the sensitivity of liver cancer detection.[85] CA19-9, a mucin-glycoprotein tumor marker, is by far the most sensitive marker for pancreatic cancer. The serum level of CA19-9 is significantly elevated in most patients with pancreatic cancer.[86]Thapa et al. used carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and PEI to construct thin films on a gold surface using a layer-by-layer (LBL) protocol. NHS-EDC was used to activate the carboxyl group on CNTs, and the anti-CA19-9 antibody was anchored on the membrane surface to form a biosensor. Li et al. prepared auPAR-targeted DGLU11 nanoprobe using endograft poly-L-lysine (DGL) as a platform for binding uPAR-targeting peptide U11, gadolinium diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (Gd DTPA) and cyanine dye cy5.5. Dual MR/near-infrared fluorescence (NIRF) targeted molecular imaging of precancerous pancreatic intraepithelial neoplasia (PanIN) and pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) lesions was performed. Shi et al. reported that Gd-doped CuS NPs combined with tumor targeting and MMP-2 can be effectively used in biomimetic/fluorescence magnetic resonance imaging of gastric cancer. A study demonstrated that T-MAN nanoprobes can identify lymph node and gastric cancer metastases in mice.[87]One of the biggest advantages of nanotechnology in cancer treatment is that it can overcome the dilemma of drug delivery and in vivo toxicity. Nanotechnology provides a platform for the delivery of insoluble or unstable drugs and improves the bioavailability and efficacy of drugs.

IN LUNG CANCER

Clinically, bronchoscopy is a useful method for evaluating lesions in the central airways, but it is an invasive procedure that can only examine a few upper bronchi. According to guidelines, clinical imaging for lung cancer includes CT, MRI, single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT), and positron emission tomography (PET). Nanotechnology is gradually improving the development of tumor diagnostics and bringing influential breakthroughs in medicine and healthcare. NPs have a number of properties that allow them to overcome the biological and chemical barriers of the human body, increase therapeutic efficacy while reducing invasiveness and optimizing biocompatibility.[88] Biomarkers associated with tumors can be found in the bloodstream using liquid biopsy, presenting a significant opportunity for early detection of lung cancer. Nanoscale extracellular vesicles (EVs) such as exosomes are small vesicles released by various cell types and are highly present in body fluids. Recently, researchers found that exosomal miRNAs such as miR-205, miR-19a, miR-19b, miR-30b, and miR-20a experienced a decrease in the blood stream after surgical removal. These compounds could potentially serve as valuable indicators for the diagnosis of squamous cell lung cancer. Potential biomarkers for the diagnosis of NSCLC include exosomal miR-126, miR-96, miR-23a, miR-30b/30c, miR-19b-3p, miR-21-5p, miR-221-3p, miR-584-5p, miR-425-5p, miR-409-3p, miR-520, miR-521 and also lncRNAs TBIL A, AG AP2-AS1,[90]. AHSG and ECM1,[90,91] Cell-free DNA (cfDNA) is released by necrotic or apoptotic cells. Compared to cell-free DNA (cfDNA), nanoscale EV-derived DNA (nEV-DNA) released from living cells contains a relatively more complete fragment and requires less plasma for detection. Wan et al. used PCR to examine nEV-DNA and cfDNA obtained from NSCLC patients and discovered a strong linear association between the amount of nEV-DNA or cfDNA and tumor volume in early stages of NSCLC. The sensitivity of nEV-DNA in the early diagnosis of NSCLC was 25.7% and 14.2%, while the specificity was 96.6% and 91.7%. These results suggest that nEV-DNA is superior to cfDNA in accurately identifying early-stage NSCLC.[89]. Biomimetic nanoengineering is emerging as a promising strategy for nanoparticle surface modification in drug-resistant EGFR-mutated NSCLC. This approach involves the use of cell membranes derived from platelets, erythrocytes, leukocytes and mesenchymal stem cells. Therefore, nanoparticles that are coated with cancer cell membrane-associated proteins can penetrate cancer cells by binding to specific isotopes. Wu et al. created bio-nanoparticles using a cancer cell membrane protein to fight drug-resistant NSCLC and improve the efficacy of chemotherapy including DOX and icotinib. In vitro, the bio-NPs demonstrated superior stability and increased homologous targeting ability compared to the control group. In vivo, the bionic nanoparticles resulted in higher tumor decrease with less side effects. [92]

IN GLIOBLASTOMA

Glioblastoma is a broad classification of tumors that develop from glial cells and neuronal cells in the nervous system. It is a prevalent type of brain tumor known for its aggressive nature and high mortality rate. In the United States, glioma has an estimated annual incidence of approximately 6 cases per 100,000 individuals. Glioblastoma accounts for roughly 60% of these cases, and men are mostly affected.[93] Currently, commonly used imaging diagnostic technologies in the treatment of glioblastoma mainly include CT, PET, MRI, etc., but these imaging technologies have their drawbacks. Therefore, it is necessary to develop new imaging techniques or contrast agents to ensure that patients with glioblastoma can receive an accurate diagnosis, which serves as a crucial first step in the effective treatment of glioblastoma.[94] With the rise of nanotechnology, diagnostic imaging technology is developing rapidly. Hou et al.[95] used a pretargeting strategy to develop PET imaging technology. To begin with, the integration of supramolecular NPs and bioorthogonal chemistry is used to synthesize tumor-targeting agents known as TCO \subset SNPs. After intravenous injection of TCO \subset SNP, the tumor EPR phenomenon facilitates the selective accumulation of TCO \subset SNP in the tumor. As TCO \subset SNPs accumulate in the tumor, they disintegrate and release TCO/CD-PEI, which is a TCO-grafted molecular building block. Subsequently, a radiolabeled reporter molecule (^{64}Cu -TZ) is administered, while TCO/CD-PEI remains present in the tumor. Subsequently, a bio-orthogonal reaction takes place, which simultaneously ensures the rapid removal of the remaining ^{64}Cu -TZ from the body. High-contrast PET imaging of the tumor is significantly enhanced due to the limitation of radioactivity in the tumor by the conjugation adduct (^{64}Cu -DHP/Cd-PEI), which leads to improved imaging quality.

IN HEMATOLOGICAL MALIGNANCIES

Early diagnosis of leukemia is essential to prevent irreversible damage and mortality. Currently, leukemia is diagnosed primarily by peripheral blood and bone marrow testing, which includes bone marrow biopsy, complete blood count (CBC), and blood smear analysis. The first technique is an extremely invasive process with complications, while the second is non-invasive but usually lacks sensitivity for early detection. The advent of nanotechnology has opened the way to a new path in the diagnosis of leukemia. Lin et al. developed a fluorescent biosensing platform. In their design, leukemia-derived exosomes can be captured by an anti-CD63 antibody on the platform. Exosomes were ligated with a set of DNA primers that specifically targeted the nucleolin recognition aptamer (AS1411), initiated the amplification reaction, and resulted in the production of a significant number of repetitive sequences. Subsequent replicates were hybridized with GNP-DNA-FAM, a gold nanoparticle conjugated to the fluorescent dye FAM. Accumulated fluorescence signals from FAM.[96] would then be detected. Ensafi et al. designed a biosensor for the identification and differentiation of two CLL variants (IgVH gene mutation status). A highly sensitive conversion platform for detection of ZAP-70 gene level and differentiation of CLL types by genetic analysis is created using gold NPs (AuNPs) coated with a ZAP-70 oligonucleotide probe on the biosensor surface.[97] Furthermore, caspase-3, a well-established indicator of cellular programmed cell death, it can be triggered by both intrinsic and extrinsic pathways of apoptosis. Detection of caspase-3 activity allows evaluation of the impact of chemotherapy.

IN OTHER CANCERS

Thyroid cancer can be categorized into two groups based on cellular origin: (1) cancers derived from follicular epithelial cells; (2) cancer derived from parafollicular cells (C cells). Follicular cancers consist of papillary, follicular, and anaplastic cancers, while C cell-derived cancers are predominantly of the medullary type. Thyroid carcinomas vary in terms of incidence and lethality, which is particularly important for differential diagnosis. Genetic and chromosomal changes can be seen in thyroid cancer cells. Abnormal alterations of the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathway are considered a major indicator for differentiated thyroid carcinomas (DTC), while RET proto-oncogene mutations for medullary thyroid carcinoma (MTC) and chromosomal abnormalities along with several mutations such as TP53 and CTNNA1 for ATC.[102–105] Thyroid cancer diagnostic research has long focused on non-invasive diagnostics. Gold, platinum, and iron oxide NPs have been fabricated as novel diagnostic tools for thyroid malignancies. Omer et al. proposed a kind of gold nanobiosensor in a sol-gel/PEG matrix to detect calcitonin, which is secreted by neuroendocrine C cells, functioning as an excellent biomarker for the early diagnosis of MTC. By determining serum calcitonin, the method offered a convenient option for the early diagnosis of MTC as well as the evaluation of the therapeutic effects of treatment. Breast cancer is the predominant malignancy in women with increasing prevalence. Breast cancer is characterized by uncontrolled cell division and proliferation in breast tissue. Breast cancer involves different forms, which are determined by the origin in the breast tissue and the extent of its spread. Nanobiosensors have shown great potential in the detection of various biomarkers, circulating tumor cells and other unique biomolecules in the diagnosis of breast cancer.[100] MicroRNA miR-99a-5p dysregulation has been identified as a reliable indicator of early breast cancer. Garrido-Cano et al., demonstrated a novel anodic alumina biosensor for breast cancer diagnosis with high sensitivity and selectivity for the detection of miR-99a-5p in plasma.

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